

FNS – Cloud

Food Nutrition Security

Food Nutrition Security Cloud

Deliverable 4.2

Food labelling data and reformulation tools

Due Date: 30.09.2021
Submission Date: 30.09.2021
Dissemination Level: Public
Lead beneficiary: NUTRIS
Main contact: Igor Pravst, igor.pravst@nutris.org

Project acronym: FNS-Cloud **Project Number:** 863059
Start date of project: 01.10.2019 **Project duration:** October 2019 – September 2023

Food Nutrition Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020-EU.3.2.2.3. – A sustainable and competitive agri-food industry) under Grant Agreement No. 863059 – www.fns-cloud.eu

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D4.2: Food labelling data and reformulation tools

Document Control Information																																					
Title	<i>D4.2 Food labelling data and reformulation tools</i>																																				
Editor	<i>Igor Pravst (NUTRIS)</i>																																				
Reviewer(s)	<i>Eileen Gibney (UCD), Kurt Gedrich (TUM), Mark Roe (EuroFIR)</i>																																				
Dissemination Level	<input type="checkbox"/> CO Confidential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU Public																																				
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Datasets underlined	Background datasets: BD11 Swiss food composition database BD12 Slovenian branded foods dataset BD13 Dutch Branded Food Database LEDA (LevensmiddelenDataBank) BD14 Open Food Facts (OFF) database Generated datasets: WP4/GD11 CLAS - Branded food composition dataset compiled in food monitoring study in Slovenia WP4/GD12 VKJ - Branded food composition dataset compiled using crowdsourcing with mobile app VesKajJes in Slovenia																																				

Version/Date	Change/Comment
<i>0.1_2021-05-12</i>	<i>Draft outline prepared by NUTRIS</i>
<i>0.2_2020-08-04</i>	<i>First version prepared by NUTRIS</i>
<i>0.3_2020-08-18</i>	<i>Second version – amendments by RIVM, JSI, PMT, GS1 in shared file</i>
<i>0.4_2020-09-13</i>	<i>Third version prepared by NUTRIS (sent to reviewers)</i>
<i>1.0_2020-09-29</i>	<i>Final version prepared by NUTRIS integrating all reviewers' comments</i>

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1. Publishable Summary

Food labelling is regulated to protect and support consumers' informed food choices, but food labels also provide useful data for user communities, e.g., food and nutrition authorities (i.e., monitor food supply and develop food policies), food businesses (i.e., insight into competition, stimulating development of new products), and researchers (i.e., dietary assessment, exploring links with noncommunicable diseases (NCDs)). In recent years, the food industry has come under increasing pressure to reformulate foods and improve their nutritional composition, i.e., to reduce salt, (saturated & trans) fats, added sugars, but in most jurisdictions, this is done on a voluntarily basis.

Cross-sectional monitoring of labelling provides important insights into supply trends and, whilst progress has been made with harmonisation of data collection, only a few countries have extensive monitoring programmes, often due to cost and time implications. The traditional approach is to take photographs of pre-packed foods in key food stores and, using data arising from this image, compile food labelling and composition databases. Product barcodes are sometimes used as product identifiers – typically this a Global Trade Item Number). The approach generates hundreds of thousands of images and involves data extraction and manipulation. Data management and analyses in such studies is complex. Furthermore, such studies need to be repeated every few years. With the growing use of smart phones and associated infrastructure (data roaming, Wi-Fi), crowdsourcing became a realistic alternative for support in compilation of labelling databases. Advantages include reduced costs, speed, flexibility, scalability, and diversity, and participation of citizens, while disadvantages are related with accuracy and duplication. In FNS-Cloud Task 4.2 we have focused on three food categories, identified as being key groups in reformulation opportunities, and thus of significant interest in the Food and Nutrition sector. For further use in WP5 demonstrator (Task 5.1.2 Food labelling data and reformulation tools) we compiled a branded food composition dataset from existing datasets (SI, CH, NL, DE), and collected two new branded food datasets (SI) with different approaches: (a) traditional cross-sectional food supply study, when researchers systematically collect food labelling data for all products in the selected food stores; and (b) crowdsourcing approach, where food labelling information is collected non-systematically by consumers with mobile app #VešKajJeš, which is in used in Slovenia. Our goal was to exploit the use of crowdsourcing as a tool for undertaking food monitoring surveys.

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CV	Cross Validation
	Composition and Labelling Information System
CLAS	(used for food monitoring in Slovenia)
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
EFSA	European Food Safety Agency
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FNS	Food, nutrition, security
OFF	Open Food Facts initiative
GDSN	Global Data Synchronisation Network (GS1 GDSN)
GFMG	Global Food Monitoring Group initiative
GPC	Global Product Classification (GS1 GPC)
GTIN	Global Trade Item Number (GS1 GTIN)
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
QUID	Quantitative Ingredient Declaration
IE	Information Extraction
RDA	Research Data Alliance
	A smartphone application VešKajJeš, used for
#VKJ	crowdsourcing in Slovenia

2. Background - food labelling and composition information

People's diets are composed from a wide variety of foods and drinks (both will be further referred to as 'foods' for the remainder of this document). In general, we can distinguish between *generic* and *branded foods*. For example, orange juice could be considered as generic food, while on the market you can find a wide variety of branded orange juices, which can also have notable differences in properties, such as taste and nutritional composition. It should be mentioned that composition of foods is sometimes regionally specific, with notable differences between countries. Such differences are more expressed for some nutrients/foods than others. For example, while amino-acid composition in most meats is relatively stable, the content of many other nutrients can also vary in foods, which are available worldwide, because of the use of different cultivars and agricultural practices, and also because the differences in soils and climatic conditions [1].

2.1 Importance of food labelling and composition information

Data about the composition of foods consumed in a population's diet is very important and has a wide variety of uses (**Table 1**). In **research** it is used in epidemiological dietary studies (for example to investigate nutrient intakes to identify populations at risk for deficiencies), in some clinical intervention trials (for example to account for dietary factors, where diets/foods are a co-founding factor in treatments) and food supply studies (for example when we are investigating time-changes in composition of foods). This data is also very important in **clinical practice** (i.e. in dietary counselling and preparation of diets for patients with special dietary needs or medical conditions), for **policy makers** (for example in assessment of food reformulation programmes and basis for evidence-based policy decisions), **business companies** (for example for identification of opportunities for improving composition of foods and for providers of IT services, where food composition data is used to support dietary, lifestyle and health objectives) and also **consumers**, to support informed selection of healthier foods and assure food safety - particularly to those with special dietary needs (including allergies).

From a public health perspective, monitoring of food composition and labelling of branded foods available in any country provides insights into the market availability and informs the development of reformulation strategies as well as the planning, implementation and monitoring of different public health interventions [2-4].

Table 1: Examples of use of food composition and labelling information

Research	Clinical practice	Policy makers	Companies	Consumers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • epidemiological dietary studies • dietary intervention studies • clinical intervention trials, where diet or foods are considered co-founding factors • food supply studies • assessment of exposure to food components 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nutritional counselling in patients • preparation of diets for patients with special dietary needs (including allergies) or medical conditions (for example diabetes) • identification of dietary risks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • basis for evidence-based food policy decisions • assessment of efficacy of food reformulation programmes • regulatory restrictions, related with specific food components (trans fats, additives...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identification of opportunities for improving composition of foods • comparisons with other foods – use of comparative nutrition claims • promotion of foods with improved nutritional composition • providers of IT services, where food composition data is used to support dietary, lifestyle and health objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • supporting informed selection of foods • enabling comparison of different foods • supporting choices of healthier foods • assuring food safety, particularly to those with special dietary needs (including allergies)

2.2 Food composition data on food labels

It should be noted that labelling information on branded foods is tightly related with requirements provided in the Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers [5] (examples provided in Supplementary Table S1). Some labelling information are always mandatory, with some voluntary, but the format is consistent which helps somewhat in the data collection.

Typical example of mandatory information is the list of food ingredients, which includes all the ingredients of the food, in descending order of weight, as recorded at the time of their use in the manufacture of the food [5]. This information is typically provided in unstructured text format (list), which can also contain embedded complex ingredients, which are themselves composed from several different constituents. As explained in **Table 2**, the list of ingredients is provided in text format and can contain complex multi-component ingredients, making it very challenging for analyses. We should also mention challenges related to language issues and names of the food ingredients.

Table 2: Example of complexity of the presentation of list of ingredients

Product	List of ingredients	Issue
<p>Nutella - Ferrero - 825 g GTIN 3017620429484</p>	<p>sugar, palm oil, hazelnuts 13%, cocoa lean to 7.4%, skimmed milk powder 6.6%, whey powder, emulsifiers: lecithins [soy], vanillin</p>	<p>While the content (%) of some ingredients is labelled, the content of others is not.</p> <p>In some constituents, raw ingredients can be also provided, i.e. due to regulation of labelling of allergens.</p>
<p>Siggi's Skyr - 150 g GTIN 3838800063218</p>	<p>Pasteurized skimmed milk, strawberry fruit preparation 12% (strawberries 44%, cane sugar, starch, concentrated lemon juice), yogurt culture.</p>	<p>Presence of embedded complex ingredient, which has its own presentation of composition.</p> <p>Some constituents can be provided with described production technology, affecting their composition.</p>

As shown in Table 2, the list of ingredients in some cases also contain information on ingredients causing allergies or intolerances, which shall according to regulation [5] be emphasised through a typeset that clearly distinguishes it from the rest of the list of ingredients. The quantity of certain ingredients is also required by food labelling regulation [5] - particularly if such ingredient appears in the name of the food or is usually associated with that name by the consumer, or if ingredient is emphasised on the labelling in words, pictures

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or graphics (details provided in Supplementary Table S1). A common term for this is Quantitative Ingredient Declaration (QUID).

In nutrition declaration values are typically expressed per 100 g and per 100 ml, with some exceptions. Nutrition declaration is also considered as mandatory labelling information (Table 3, Supplementary Table S1). The mandatory part of the nutrition declaration includes (a) energy value; and the amounts of (b) fat, (c) saturates, (d) carbohydrate, (e) sugars, (f) protein and (g) salt. However, following additional parts of the nutrition declaration are non-mandatory or conditionally mandatory: amounts of (a) mono-unsaturates; (b) polyunsaturates; (c) polyols; (d) starch; (e) fibre; and (f) vitamins or minerals. Food manufacturer can decide to include any of these information on food label, using in regulated format [5]. However, if such nutrients/constituents are mentioned in nutrition or health claims on the label, their inclusion into nutrient declaration is conditionally mandatory [6].

Table 3: Example of nutrition declaration with (conditionally) mandatory information for a case products: Crunchy Corn Tortilla Chips (Old El Paso - 185 g; GTIN 8410076482655)

Nutrition facts	Unit	As sold for 100 g	Mandatory information
Energy	Kcal	551 kcal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Energy	kJ	2,305 kJ	
Fat	g	33.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Saturated fat	g	4.3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Carbohydrates	g	54.3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Sugars	g	0.5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Fibre	g	3.9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> *
Proteins	g	5.5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Salt	g	0.97	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Vitamin C...	mg/...	not provided	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

*Note: Conditionally mandatory (if fibre is mentioned in nutrition/health claim)

2.3 Sources of food composition information

In the past food composition datasets for generic foods were mostly used for research purposes. While composition of generic foods is occasionally revisited, and updated, such nutritional values are mostly considered as fixed. Databases covering these generic foods typically contain a few hundreds of **generic foods**, but nowadays people's diets contain a mix of basic foods (listed in generic food composition databases) as well as processed pre-packed – '**branded foods**', which are not typically listed in national food composition datasets. Unlike generic foods, food manufacturers are regularly changing composition of their branded products to address consumers' expectations and regulatory requirements, while some foods are removed from the market, and new ones are being launched [7].

Datasets with branded food composition and labelling information originate from a variety of sources. One source are data received directly from **food manufacturers** (Table 4), but their

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participation with the provision of this food composition information to database compilers is voluntary. Food companies rarely decide to share this information to open databases, and if they do, they often only share some of the required information (e.g. information for nutritional labelling of products). There are some good examples of such a collaborative approach for creating branded food datasets [8-12], but such approaches typically do not capture the dynamic changes of the food market. The progress in the standardisation of this area also needs to be noted. Branded foods are usually labelled with EAN/UPC barcodes [13], which are designed for the high-volume scanning environment and therefore suitable for the retail point-of-sale (POS). EAN-13 barcodes are mostly used in Europe. Each barcode is linked with a unique product identifier – usually this is the GS1 Global Trade Item Number (GTIN) [14]; in the GTIN Register food name is considered as mandatory attribute, while food composition data are not included. We should mention that GS1 also maintain Global Data Synchronisation Network (GDSN), a globally operating standardised network that enables exchange of all types of master product data (including food labelling and composition data) between brand owners, manufacturers, suppliers, distributors and retailers [15]. In the GDSN, based on the Global Data Model [16], specific food labelling parameters are considered a mandatory information, however the use of GDSN is voluntary, meaning that not all items in the GTIN Register have a corresponding record in the GDSN. Furthermore, GDSN record is only available for subscribers, and not open access. Typical alternative sources of food composition information nowadays include databases compiled using (a) data collected in **food monitoring studies**; and (b) data collected with exploitation of **crowdsourcing** (Table 4).

Table 4: Typical sources of branded food composition and labelling information

Food manufacturers	Food monitoring	Crowdsourcing
sharing food composition information to databases (voluntarily)	analyses of available foods (not feasible on large scale) data collections from food labels in food stores web-scraping: data collections from on-line sources (on-line shops, web pages of food producers)	enabling consumers to collect and share data on the composition of foods, i.e., through smart-phone or web applications

2.3.1 Food monitoring studies

Food monitoring studies typically refer to gathering information about food available in the food supply in any given market (country, region) using a variety of methods, firstly direct analysis of a subset of food(s) or secondly collection of data from food packaging of available

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foods, including ingredient and nutrition information. Finally, the information can be provided directly by food manufacturers.

Foods available to consumers, could in theory be continuously analysed, however this process is both time consuming, technically difficult and expensive, and as such alternative approaches are preferred. In the case of prepacked (branded) foods, the Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers [5] requires manufacturers to disclose key food facts on food labels. Food labels are therefore additional sources of data that can be used in the food monitoring process. In the European Union labelling of food ingredients (including additives and allergens) and nutrition declaration is mandatory. By law this information also needs to be provided for all foods, available in on-line stores [5]. Food labelling thus provides other routes for data collection, without direct analysis and/or participation of food manufacturers.

Considering that chemical analyses of thousands of available foods is not a feasible option, the traditional approach for collection of branded food information are cross-sectional food monitoring studies in supermarkets, where data is extracted from food labels [17-19]. A methodological approach for conduction of such studies was harmonised within the Global Food Monitoring Group in 2013 [18] and INFORMAS programme in 2015 [20, 21]; these protocols support the regional collection of data on food composition and labelling in all major food suppliers, preferably with the collection of food photographs, across all available food categories. However, such approach is hardly feasible in practice, because such data collection is expensive and time-consuming. Therefore, food monitoring studies are commonly conducted with partial data collection (with focus on selected food categories and in selected food shops), and not very often (typically every few years) [22].

The complexity of this type of data collection can be presented in the example of food supply studies, conducted in Slovenia. The first food monitoring study in Slovenia was completed in 2011 to support a research project V7-1107 'Nutrition and health claims on foods' [23]. In the absence of international recommendations to conduct this type of study, this initial study only focused on selected food categories in three major food retailers. In this study, in the food stores researchers extracted food labelling information directly into SQL database, using local notepad computers (in the food store). Special software was developed for this data collection [23]; the data only included text information, without any pictures. Altogether, nutrition declaration data from 6,348 foods were collected. While this process was very challenging the collected data was extremely valuable. A decision was therefore taken to develop an infrastructure to support more efficient food monitoring studies. An on-line tool CLAS (Composition and Labelling Information System) was developed, together with a special mobile application, to support data extraction and analyses [24]. The infrastructure of the CLAS web platform and mobile application is inter-connected, enabling data collection with less burden. The CLAS mobile application can be used for real-time collection by several researchers at the same time, without risk of duplication of work, as barcodes are used as unique identification for this purpose, thus ensuring data from a given food is only collected once. In food store the researcher scans the barcode of a product, and if data from this product has not yet collected in the cross-sectional study, the mobile application require researcher to take photos of all sides of the food packaging, and to insert information on price. Timestamp (date, time) and food store identificatory are saved automatically. All these data and images are directly sent from the mobile app to the on-line CLAS environment, where they are checked for quality (with

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the use of both automatic controls and a manual check of each product by the researcher), following by previously described data extraction process (product name, packaging, ingredients, all data from nutrition declaration) [24]. If product with same barcode was already collected, only store identification is saved to the database, and the researcher is notified that product information is already collected – thus removing duplication of work. Data extraction is completed in an on-line CLAS environment, with support of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technology, supported by manual work and cross-checking [24].

All further food monitoring studies in Slovenia were conducted with such an approach, employing data extraction from food labelling photographs. With this approach, the second food monitoring study in Slovenia was done in 2015 on selected food categories, and included N=10,694 foods, while the study in 2017 (N=21,090) covered all food groups (Table 5).

Table 5: Example of past food monitoring studies conducted in Slovenia (2011-2017)

Year	2011	2015	2017
No. of foods	6,348	10,694	21,090
Sample	Selected food categories	Selected food categories	All food categories
Notes	Manual collection of data from food labels in food stores.	Collection of data using CLAS system from pictures of food labels, taken in food stores. All pictures are archived.	Collection of data using CLAS system from pictures of food labels, taken in food stores. All pictures are archived.
Included retailers	Mercator/Spar/Hofer	Mercator/Spar/Hofer	Mercator/Spar/Tuš/Hofer/Lidl

Harmonised data collection enables international comparisons of specific food products [25, 26]. However, while occasional cross-sectional food monitoring studies are a traditional approach for research in food supply, there are several challenges – particularly related with keeping branded food composition up to date with newly launched and reformulated products [7, 12]. Additional methods are therefore important, to enable more frequent data collections.

The food retail environment is increasing in complexity. While the majority of the foods are still sold in classic food stores (i.e. supermarkets), on-line shops are also gaining importance. Most recently the COVID-19 epidemic increased use of on-line food purchases [27], which resulted in further development of online stores and more foods available by delivery. While such e-shops still sell fewer foods than classic supermarkets, it is expected that at least market-leading brands are also available on-line, making such environments very interesting for data collection. Exploiting the potential of this market, recently, an automated big data analysis approach was considered in the UK, where Harrington et al. tested weekly extraction of food products' data from supermarkets' webpages [28], allowing timely observations of changes in the marketplace.

2.3.2 Use of crowdsourcing

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Although there are several definitions of crowdsourcing, in general, this term is used for outsourcing different tasks to a crowd of people to complete them; the crowdsourcer can be an organisation or an individual [29]. Crowdsourcing is an innovative approach which is often used for tasks where a vast amount of data needs to be collected and therefore can benefit from a larger group of people completing the task. Advantages include reduced costs, speed, flexibility, scalability, and diversity, and participation of citizens, while disadvantages are related with accuracy and duplication. While crowdsourcing has rapidly developed in informational sciences, its application in public health and nutrition is also very promising [30, 31]. With the rise of mobile phone applications and similar technologies, an innovative way to access and interpret different types of information became widely available. Such platforms can commonly serve as an interface to collect crowdsourcing data.

In the context of food monitoring, these emerging new methods and associated technologies create new opportunities to keep up with the rapid changes in the food chain with less effort. A method of data collection, using crowdsourcing gives the opportunity to capture food market changes more regularly and at a considerably reduced cost [32]. Such an approach was first used in Australia with a launch of the FoodSwitch application for smartphones to collect branded food composition information and yielded impressive results [33]. A particular innovation in the application was the incorporation of a crowdsourcing function whereby users were able to contribute information on missing or new products. The crowdsourcing tool within the app has enabled a substantial expansion of the underlying database. This showed that an extensive volume of crowdsourced data provided an effective way for real-time and inexpensive tracking of nutritional composition of foods in the food supply [32] and revealed a unique opportunity for using such approach in other countries [34]. Another attempt to collate nutritional information database from data provided on food packaging using crowdsourcing was through the use of a web application; examples of such databases are Open Food Facts [35] and The Open Food Repo [36]. The advantage of such web platforms is the ability to collect data from food labels from many countries worldwide, providing insights about food composition on global markets [37-39].

Similarly, in Slovenia a smartphone application called “VešKajJeš” (#VKJ; English translation: You know what you eat) was launched in 2019 as part of the collaborative IRIO project of the Nutrition Institute (project leader), ‘Jožef Stefan’ Institute and Slovenian Consumer Organisation, and supported by the Slovenian Ministry of Health. The primary goal of this mobile application is to provide consumers with easy and quick access to data on food composition, while at the same time it facilitates consumer understanding of the data and thus promotes healthier food choices. The crowd sourcing function of the application is activated when an app user scans a food barcode which is either not yet included in the branded food database, or when there is a difference between the nutritional composition of the scanned food and the information presented in the mobile app #VKJ.

3. Objectives

The main objectives of the task are

- O1) to compile branded food composition datasets for four countries (CH, DE, NL, SI) using existing databases
- O2): to collect new branded food composition data in one country (SI) using (a) traditional data collection in food stores, and (b) data collection with crowd sourcing
- O3) a case study with a comparison of both new datasets (SI), providing insights on the potential of crowd sourcing for collecting new data

The objective of the latter case study was to compare data on average values of selected nutrients within specific food categories, simultaneously obtained using two methods: 1) crowdsourcing data obtained from users of mobile app VešKajJeš; and 2) data compiled using standardised food monitoring study in grocery stores of major retailers in Slovenia). This will provide insights about differences between the datasets.

Compiled datasets will support conduction of WP5 Demonstration tasks (datasets available for further analyses for four countries: CH, DE, NL, SI).

3.1 Scope: Selection and definition of food groups

We focused on following three food categories that are important for reformulation strategies:

- Beverages: Soft Drinks;
- Cereals and Cereal products: Breakfast cereals;
- and Dairy: Yoghurt products.

In the absence of harmonised food categorisation system, that would be used across all available food composition databases, the selected food categories were detailedly defined with inclusion parameters, assuring that datasets contain all relevant products. Description of selected food categories is provided in Table 6. Exclusion parameters are also defined, enabling conduction of tasks, comparing different datasets.

3.2 Target audience

The target audience for the food composition datasets are developers of the FNS cloud, and end users. Target audience include researchers, clinical practice policy makers, food manufacturers and end consumers (see also Table 1). Therefore, the results of this task will feed into WP5 demonstrator (Task 5.1.2 Food labelling data and reformulation tools), where use of food composition data will be exploited.

The target audience for testing the concept of the use of crowd sourcing for collecting food labelling and composition data are particularly researchers and policy makers, seeking for additional data collection methods, which could substitute or amend traditional data collection in food stores.

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Table 6: Definition of selected food categories

Food category	Food products Included	Food products Excluded
Soft drinks and beverages	<p>Water based carbonated and non-carbonated drinks with and without sugar added, with and without additives and sweeteners:</p> <p>Functional drinks, soft drinks, Cola type drinks, energy drinks, isotonic, sports drinks, flavoured water.</p>	<p>Drinking water (carbonated/non-carbonated), 100% fruit juices, fruit nectars as defined in Council Directive 2001/112/EC of 20 December 2001 relating to fruit juices and certain similar products intended for human consumption, Coffee, ingredients for coffee or tea or infusions, cocoa, herbal and other teas and infusion, milk and dairy products, fruit syrups, squashes and cordials, and powders for drinks preparation, beverage concentrates, milk and nut based drinks, alcoholic drinks, coffee replacers, chocolate containing drinks.</p>
Breakfast cereals	<p>Ready to eat breakfast cereals (with and without sugar and other ingredients and additives) (only milk/yoghurt/water to be added, no need for cooking/heating).</p> <p>Breakfast cereals plain, breakfast cereals, cereal flakes and similar, cereal rolled grains (oats and mixes), mixed breakfast cereal, muesli and similar breakfast, muesli plain, popped cereals, processed and mixed breakfast cereal, granola-type breakfast cereals, instant oatmeal, farina, corn flakes, puffed wheat or rice, multi-grain (e.g. rice, wheat and corn) breakfast cereals, mueslis, breakfast cereals made from soy or bran, and extruded-type breakfast cereals made from grain flour or powder, precooked cereals.</p>	<p>100% bran, whole unprocessed grains that need heat treatment e.g. millet, buckwheat,... cornmeal mush, wheat semolina, breakfast cereals for infants, rice, couscous etc</p>
Yoghurt and similar products (incl. yoghurt imitates)	<p>Flavoured fermented milk and fermented milk drinks (cow, goat, sheep,...): Yoghurt/ sour milk/ butter milk/ probiotic milk drinks (Actimel, Yakult)/ Skyr/ Quark/ Greek yoghurt with added ingredients or additives with fruit/cereals/ chocolate added as ingredient</p> <p>Plain yoghurt (unflavoured, no added sugar), whey drink</p> <p>This category also include yoghurt imitates (based on soy, rice, almond, coconut,...)</p>	<p>Frozen items</p> <p>Items with breakfast cereals on top (separated - to be mixed with yoghurt)</p> <p>Pudding, milk rice, panna cotta</p> <p>Milk desserts, including cottage-cheese based milk products</p>

4. Compilation of branded food composition datasets using existing datasets

4.1 Selected datasets

This subtask is addressing Objective O1: Compilation of branded food composition datasets for four countries from using existing databases (SI, CH, NL, DE).

A dataset of branded food labelling/composition was compiled for four countries (SI, CH, NL, DE) using existing data. We used branded food database, originating from three national branded food databases (CH, SI and NL dataset) and branded food database, originating from a web based crowdsourcing study (DE dataset).

It should be noted that these datasets were collected outside FNS-Cloud and can be subject to access/use restrictions. While crowdsourcing DE dataset is open-access, other three datasets (SI, NH, NL) are not published and were provided by project partners specifically for exploitation and demonstrations within FNS Cloud project.

4.1.1 Netherland (NL)

Description of source: Labelling and food composition data was extracted from the Dutch Branded Food Database LEDA (LevensmiddelenDataBank) [12]. This database is part of the NethFIR data collection that also includes the Dutch national food composition database for generic foods NEVO, the Dutch supplement database NES and the Dutch portion size database. Databases are maintained by the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) and the Netherlands Nutrition Centre (NNC). The LEDA database contained over 100,000 food items in 2020 and covers approximately 75% of the foods sold in Dutch supermarkets. Data are compiled through collaborations with data providers, which are either intermediate companies such as GS1 and Brandbank or supermarket chains or individual supermarkets. Data is exchanged and thus updated on a daily basis using APIs. All foods that are uploaded for the first time are checked using automated control procedures and are approved by a nutritionist before entering the database. Foods that are uploaded again overnight are automatically approved when passing the control procedure correctly.

The power of this dataset lies in the large and still increasing number of branded foods and the automated daily updates. However, checking still takes a considerable amount of time and some major retailers are still missing. In addition, in the data provided some information is missing and technical challenges are faced with respect to data description and completeness and consistency of data. The LEDA data is used in the 'KiesIkGezond?' mobile application (English translation: Is my food choice healthy?).

Data access status: External data with restricted access (only for use within FNS Cloud). Individual data cannot be published. The LEDA dataset can be used only by the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM; project partner) for their research and public education purposes.

Parameters in the dataset included product unique identifiers (GTIN), product/brand name (food name as provided by data provider) and food category (Global Product Classification (GPC) code at brick level; [40]), ingredient list, identification if raw or cooked, cooking instructions as

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given on the label; mandatory remarks according to EU1169/2011; portion size; packaging quantity (netto content of the package); unit for nutrient declaration of food (in gram or ml); company name; Global Location Number (GLN); information form nutrition declaration (energy, protein, fat, saturated fatty acids, carbohydrates, sugars, salt).

4.1.2 Switzerland (CH)

Description of source: The Swiss data comes from the V5.3 of the Swiss food composition database published by BLV (The Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office) in 2017 on their website <https://naehrwertdaten.ch/en/>. The data were collected and managed using FoodCASE software and a new version is published annually and is openly available, but recent version does not contain branded products anymore. The used version of the dataset (V5.3) contains around 1000 generic foods and over 9500 branded foods, mainly from Swiss own-brand retailers: Migros and Coop. The data were compiled by contacting the producers and receiving the data from them. It should be noted that in Switzerland a new branded data study is being conducted by BLV, but the data are not yet available.

Data access status: External data with restricted access (only for use within FNS Cloud). Individual data cannot be published.

Parameters in the dataset included product unique identifiers (ID; ID V 4.0; ID SwissFIR), product name/synonyms and food category (Product category; level D-F-I-E); Specific gravity and information form nutrition declaration (including energy, protein, fat, saturated fatty acids, carbohydrates, sugars, salt).

4.1.3 Slovenia (SI)

Description of data source: Cross-sectional data on available foods and their composition were retrieved from the Composition and Labelling Information System (CLAS) database of the Nutrition Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia (NUTRIS). The most recent available full food supply market dataset was used, with data collection in 2017. Data collection methodology was previously described [41]. Monitoring was conducted in retailers that represent the majority of the national food market share: Mercator, Spar, Tuš, Lidl and Hofer. Foods in the dataset are categorised according to the classification proposed by Global Food Monitoring Group [42]. The full 2017 dataset contained a total of 21,090 products.

Data access status: External data with restricted access (only for use within FNS Cloud). Individual data cannot be published.

Parameters in the dataset included product unique identifiers (record ID, barcode number usually GTIN), product name and food category (GFMG category), packaging quantity, ingredient list, and mandatory information form nutrition declaration (energy, fat, saturated fat, carbohydrates, fibre, protein, salt).

4.1.4 Germany (DE)

Description of source: Food composition and labelling data was downloaded from the open access *Open food facts (OFF)* platform [35]. Open Food Facts is a collaborative project with contributors from all around the world. The contributors to the OFF are mostly citizens, although the platform

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also enable inclusion of data directly from food producers. Contributors are volunteers. The contributors send pictures of the product, its labels, ingredients lists and nutrition facts table. To detect potential errors more easily, some automated checks are implemented. Datasets are available through APIs. Complete datasets can be also downloaded. Platform cover different countries, including Germany.

Data access status: External data with open access.

Parameters in the dataset included product unique identifiers (barcode number usually GTIN), url address; product name and food category (OFF category), packaging quantity, packaging details (packaging, packaging_tags, packaging_text), brand, ingredient list, allergens, serving size, additives, and mandatory information form nutrition declaration (energy, fat, saturated fat, carbohydrates, fibre, protein, salt).

4.2 Data harmonisation approach

As highlighted in previous deliverables (including D2.1 and D3.2), the FNS data are heterogeneous in data types and formats: The inventory of existing FNS data (FNS inventory, 2020) showed that FNS data elements from both public and proprietary data sources are stored in heterogeneous *data formats*, ranging from simple files to structured databases that are often application specific. For example, some data are stored in unstructured or semi-structured formats (plain text files, HTML or XML files, binary files), while some data are stored in spreadsheets as well as in structured relational databases. This was also observed specifically in the food labelling datasets. A harmonisation was focused on information needed for WP5 demonstrator (Task 5.1.2 Food labelling data and reformulation tools), using data available in the above-mentioned datasets. Available parameters for all four datasets were compared to identify key parameters, contained in all the datasets.

The structure of each of the datasets was very different, with some providing less or more details for each product in the dataset. For example, the Dutch (NL) dataset contained identification if product is raw or cooked, and cooking instructions as given on the label, while such information was not provided in other datasets. Furthermore, while some standardised datasets were mostly complete (providing complete data for most of the items in the dataset), this was not the case in the crowdsourcing dataset (DE), where data are provided by end users - volunteers.

Due to these variations, the following decisions with respect to data harmonisation were taken in consultation with all relevant partners and stakeholder to ensure the development of the required harmonised dataset to be used in WP5:

- (1) Foods are to be included in the harmonised dataset, if at least name and energy content are provided. Other information such as content of other nutrients and food ingredients might be missing (either not present on food label, or not extracted from the label), but once food description and energy content were available the food was included.
- (2) Data was harmonised to assure comparability, with the following considerations:
 - a. Product name is inserted in original form and language. If the original dataset contained the food name in different formats (i.e. brand name, short name, long

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- name), in the harmonised database product name was constructed with concentrate function, starting with brand name.
- b. In some datasets energy/nutritional composition was provided per 100 g or mL, while in other energy/nutrients was provided in specific amounts (i.e., on portion size, package, etc). To standardise, all energy/nutritional composition data was transformed to per 100 g or mL.
 - c. Sodium content was re-calculated into salt content (using conversion factor 1 g salt = 2.54 g sodium chloride/salt).
 - d. Where available; content of dietary fibre was also included, although this is voluntarily food labelling information and as such was not available for most foods.
- (3) Original datasets were exported with consideration of inclusion criteria provided in Table 6. However, due to different food categorisations systems used in the original datasets, we were unable to automatically exclude some products, which were not in our scope (see excluded product groups in the Table 6). For example, when food category with yoghurts was included from a specific data source, the data export could also contain some types of foods, which are meeting our exclusion criteria (i.e. frozen yoghurt, yoghurts with breakfast cereals on top [separated - to be mixed with yoghurt], milk desserts). We decided not to remove these items from the harmonised database, to enable possible changes in the exclusion criteria during data processing in the WP5.
- (4) The following data are collected for all items (with missing information, where data was not available):
- a. EAN Barcode number (usually GTIN; not provided in the CH dataset)
 - b. Brand + Product name
 - c. Product category
 - d. Packaging quantity
 - e. Ingredient list
 - f. Nutrition declaration: Energy per 100 g or mL
 - g. Nutrition declaration: Fat per 100 g or mL
 - h. Nutrition declaration: Saturated fat per 100 g or mL
 - i. Nutrition declaration: Carbohydrates per 100 g or mL
 - j. Nutrition declaration: Sugar per 100 g or mL
 - k. Nutrition declaration: Fibre per 100 g or mL
 - l. Nutrition declaration: Protein per 100 g or mL
 - m. Nutrition declaration: Salt per 100 g or mL

5. Collection of new branded food composition datasets for Slovenia

This subtask is addressing Objective O2: Collection of new branded food composition data in one country (SI) using (a) traditional data collection in food stores, and (b) data collection with crowd sourcing and with new data collections.

5.1 Traditional data collection in food stores

Data collection: A cross-sectional study was conducted in Slovenia to collect representative data about the composition/labelling of branded foods in the food supply. We used standardised approach for data collection from food labels in food stores [17-19].

Data was collected in year 2020 in six major food retailers in Slovenia, covering majority of national food supply. Following food stores in the capital region (Ljubljana, Slovenia) were included:

- Hipermarket Šiška
- Interspar Vič
- Tuš Vič
- Hofer Brdo
- Eurospin Brdo
- Lidl Bežigrad

Previously mentioned on-line tool CLAS (Composition and Labelling Information System) used to support data extraction and analyses [24]. CLAS mobile application was used for real-time collection by several researchers at same time, without risks for duplication of work. Product EAN barcodes were used to assign foods with unique identification number (in most cases this was GTIN, with exception of some foods in discounter stores, which were not labelled using GS1 barcode standards). Mobile data collection app is used in a way, that researcher scan barcode of a product. If this product was not yet collected in a 2020 cross-sectional study, researcher is required to take photos of all sides of the food packaging, and to collect price. Timestamp (date, time) and food store identificatory are saved automatically. In real-time the data is then automatically sent from the mobile data collection app to on-line CLAS environment, where it is checked for quality (with the use of both automatic controls and a manual check of each product by the researcher) [24]. If researchers scan a barcode of a product, which was previously recorded in same cross-sectional study (i.e. by another researcher or in other food store), only store identification is saved to the database. Data extraction was done in an on-line CLAS environment, with support of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technology, but still with a lot of manual work and cross-checking [24]. Export was done for unique valid items, for which nutrition declaration was provided. Altogether, 28.028 unique food items were found on the Slovenian marketplace.

Data access status: Internal data collected within FNS cloud; open access will be assured within FNS Cloud project

Parameters in the dataset included product unique identifiers (record ID, barcode number usually GTIN), product name and food category (GFMG category), packaging quantity, ingredient

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list, and mandatory information form nutrition declaration (energy, fat, saturated fat, carbohydrates, fibre, protein, salt).

5.2 Collecting new data: crowdsourcing

Data collection: Data was collected with the use of smartphone application VešKajJeš (#VKJ; Engl. Transl.: You know what you eat), launched in Slovenia in 2019 as part of the collaborative IRIO project, supported by Slovenian Ministry of Health. Primary goal of #VKJ app is to provide consumers with easy and quick access to data on food composition, while at the same time it facilitated their interpretation of the data and thus promote healthier food choices. App is available to smartphone users with Android and iOS systems. App enable users (consumer) to scan barcode (EAN) of selected food and receive feedback information on the product's nutritional composition and provide the interpretation of the nutritional information based on the nutrient profiling with food traffic light labelling system. The crowd sourcing function of the application is activated in situation, when app user scans a barcode of food, which is either not yet included in the branded food database, or when a difference between the nutritional composition of actual food and the information presented in the #VKJ.

Crowdsourcing information were collected in a special environment (bazil.si), which was developed by 'Jožef Stefan' Institute within the IRIO project. In the bazil.si data is extracted from the pictures of food labels using prioritisation system. Data extraction is assured for all items with a minimum of three unique searches by app users. Altogether, 7.463 unique food products were used for data extraction in period 2019-2020.

Data access status: Internal data collected within FNS cloud; open access will be assured within FNS Cloud project

Parameters in the dataset: included product unique identifiers (product code, EAN, last_modified; shop_info), product name and food category (product group IS, product group name); and mandatory information form nutrition declaration [Def_unit_macro] (energy, fat, saturated fat, carbohydrates, fibre, protein, salt).

6. Case study: potential of crowd sourcing for collecting new branded food data

This subtask is addressing Objective O3: *a case study with a comparison of both new datasets (SI), providing insights on to evaluate the potential of crowd sourcing for collecting new data*

6.1 Datasets and comparison approach

Comparison was done between two datasets with newly collected data:

A: CLAS dataset: Datasets with branded food composition data, collected in Slovenian food stores, as described in Chapter 5.1

B: VKJ dataset: Dataset with branded food composition data, collected with the use of crowdsourcing with mobile app VešKajJeš in the BAZIL environment, as described in Chapter 5.2

Both datasets were exported from the SQL database into Excel spreadsheets, where data cleaning and comparisons were conducted. The following food (sub)categories were selected for analysis: Beverages (Fruit and vegetable juices: Juices, Nectars, Soft drinks: Energy drinks, Soft drinks (incl. Electrolyte drinks)); Cereal and cereal products: Breakfast cereals, Cereal flakes and bran, Dairy; Yoghurt products: Flavoured yogurt, Flavoured yogurt drinks, Plain yogurt, Yogurt imitates. Only items with available energy content data were included. For each food (sub)category from CLAS/VKJ dataset, number of unique food products is provided, together with content of energy, fat, saturated fat, protein, carbohydrate, sugar, dietary fibre, and salt was calculated. For each (sub)category, average content of energy (ENE; kJ); fat (g); saturated fat (FASAT; g); proteins (PROT; g); carbohydrates (CH; g); sugar (SUG; g), dietary fibre (FIB; g) and salt (g) was calculated, separately for CLAS and VKJ dataset. For energy and sugar content comparison between the datasets, median, average and standard deviation was also calculated. Considering that energy/sugar were not normally distributed (Shapiro–Wilk test) in all subcategories, Wilcoxon's test was used to check for differences between datasets. Significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

6.2 Results of comparison and discussion

The food monitoring study dataset (CLAS) was notably larger, in comparison with the crowdsourcing dataset (VKJ) (**Table 7**). Beverages were the food category with the largest number of products in the VKJ dataset (N=334, particularly Soft drinks: N=200), while both Cereal and cereal products (N=239; particularly Breakfast cereals: N=225) and yoghurts (N=217) were quite comparable. Similar trends were also observed in the CLAS dataset (1664 beverages, while number of cereals and yoghurts were 546 and 867, respectively), but n values larger.

Comparison of average nutritional composition for energy and selected nutrients (fat; saturated fat; proteins; carbohydrates; sugar, dietary fibre and salt) in the selected food (sub)categories is presented in **Table 7**. Considering that this task was focused into three categories, where food reformulation is most commonly focused into sugar reduction, comparison of energy values and sugar content is particularly relevant.

Median and average energy content and results of statistical comparison between both datasets are shown in **Table 9**. Yoghurts was the only main food category, where we observed a statistically significant difference in energy between the two datasets ($p=0.017$). In beverages we observed

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some significant differences in the sub-categories of nectars ($p=0.003$) and soft drinks ($p=0.015$). No significant differences were observed among breakfast cereals.

In beverages median energy content was 33.7 kJ/100 mL for both the VKJ and CLAS dataset. This category was divided into fruit and vegetable juices (including nectars) – where median energy content was more comparable in juices (47.8 vs. 46.6 kJ) than in nectars (43.0 vs. 47.8 kJ); and soft drinks, where significantly ($p=0.015$) higher median energy content was observed in the dataset originating from monitoring in food stores (21.1 vs. 29.0 kJ). Looking into both subcategories of soft drinks (energy drinks, other soft drinks), differences were not statistically significant, although a trend of higher energy content was observed for the CLAS dataset (other soft drinks: 22.2 vs 27.1 kJ; energy drinks: 10.5 vs. 45.6 kJ).

Interestingly, the difference in median energy content in breakfast cereals was minor (387.1 vs. 388.1 kJ/100g for VKJ and CLAS, respectively). As expected, higher median energy content was observed in the processed breakfast cereals (392.2 and 391.7 kJ), than in cereal flakes and brans (338.9 and 365.9 kJ).

Yoghurts were the only food category in our comparison, where a significant difference was observed between both datasets on the level of main food category. Contrary to the situation in beverages, in yoghurts slightly higher median energy levels were observed in the crowd sourced VKJ dataset (84.6 vs. 82.5 kJ/100g). To provide further insights on these differences, this category was divided into flavoured yoghurt, flavoured yoghurt drinks, plain yoghurt and yoghurt imitates. It turned out that flavoured yoghurts and yoghurts imitates were sub-categories with statistically significant difference ($p\leq 0.001$). However, contrary trend was observed in flavoured yoghurts (89.1 vs. 94.1 kJ) in comparison with yoghurt imitates (94.6 vs 78.7 kJ). Median energy content was almost the same in both datasets in flavoured yoghurt drinks (75.6 vs 73.8 kJ) and in plain yoghurts (59.5 vs 59.2 kJ).

While food energy content is affected by the content of macronutrients, the content of sugar can be considered as a more sensitive parameter for changes in the reformulation. As shown in Table 9, we observed somewhat more statistically significant differences between the VKJ and CLAS dataset, as in case of energy content.

In beverages significantly higher mean sugar content was observed in the CLAS dataset (7.4 vs. 8.4 g sugar/100 mL; $p=0.023$). The difference was not significant in subcategory of fruit and vegetable juices, neither in their both sub-categories of nectars (10.0 vs 10.2 g) and juices (9.6 g in both datasets). Among soft drinks, significant difference was observed in the energy drinks, where majority of crowd-sourced items were sugar-free (0.0 vs. 10.6g; $p=0.005$). However, in other soft drinks the difference was not significant (5.0 vs 6.1 g).

Among breakfast cereals, cereal flakes and brans contained very low average sugar content in both datasets (1.1 vs 1.0g/100 g). As expected, a much higher content of sugar was observed in processed cereals – with higher median in the CLAS dataset (18.0 vs. 16.0 g, $p<0.001$). This observation is not in line with comparison on the energy content (Table 8), indicating that other nutrients must have affected the comparison. As can be seen in Table 7, processed breakfast cereals in the CLAS dataset also had higher average fibre content, and slightly lower fat content.

In yoghurt products, the differences in median sugar content in both datasets (11.0 vs 10.7 g sugar/100g) is minor. The only statistically significant difference was observed in the yoghurt imitates (11.3 vs. 6.1g), as was the case in the energy content. Minor differences were observed

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among plain yoghurts (4.3 g in both datasets), flavoured yoghurts (12.0 vs. 12.1 g) and flavoured yoghurt drinks (11.4 vs 11.3g).

Considering that both datasets were collected on the same market and in comparable time-period, the observed differences are obviously originating from the methodological approach of the used data collection. While traditional food supply study in food stores collect data for all the available products, regardless of their market-share, we could speculate that product market-shares are affecting data collection with crowdsourcing. With more products sold and higher penetration of the usage of specific product among consumers, there is also a higher chance that such product will be scanned with mobile app. This hypothesis should be verified in further studies.

Another reason for the observed differences between both datasets should be also mentioned. While the traditional food supply study in food stores collect data systematically for all products which are present at the observation period, it could be expected that crowdsourcing is particularly focused into newly launched items. This is because of the fact, that consumers might be more interested about the newly observed products, and also because 'older' products might be already included into branded food composition database, meaning that users of crowdsourcing app are less stimulated to send their data. Further studies should therefore focus into exploitation of the use of crowdsourcing particularly for quicker identification of newly launched food products, which are gaining high attraction to consumers.

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Table 7: Comparison of Comparison of average nutritional composition for the selected food categories (per 100 g or mL of food/drink)

Category	Crowdsourcing dataset (VKJ)									Food monitoring study dataset (CLAS)								
	N	ENE	FAT	FASAT	PROT	CH	SUG	FIBT	SALT	N	ENE	FAT	FASAT	PROT	CH	SUG	FIB	SALT
Beverages	333	33.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	7.3	6.9	0.1	0.1	1664	35.8	0.2	0.1	0.2	8.2	7.6	0.4	0.0
Fruit and vegetable juices	133	46.0	0.7	0.5	0.4	9.3	8.7	0.2	0.0	596	47.6	0.4	0.2	0.4	10.6	9.5	0.8	0.0
Juices	106	47.8	0.9	0.7	0.5	9.3	8.6	0.2	0.0	368	45.6	0.2	0.1	0.4	10.2	9.2	0.8	0.0
Nectars	27	38.8	0.1	0.0	0.3	9.2	9.0	0.1	0.1	228	50.9	0.6	0.4	0.3	11.0	10.1	0.5	0.0
Soft drinks	200	24.9	0.0	0.1	0.1	6.0	5.7	0.0	0.1	1068	29.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	6.9	6.6	0.1	0.0
Energy drinks	18	20.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.6	3.3	0.0	0.1	138	33.3	0.0	0.0	0.1	7.7	7.5	0.1	0.1
Other soft drinks	182	25.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	6.3	6.0	0.0	0.0	930	28.6	0.1	0.0	0.1	6.8	6.5	0.2	0.0
Breakfast cereals	239	392.6	9.3	3.1	9.8	63.7	14.0	7.0	0.4	546	396.8	9.1	2.7	10.4	64.2	15.9	8.1	0.4
Breakfast cereals	225	394.6	9.6	3.2	9.6	64.1	14.8	6.7	0.4	486	401.2	9.5	2.9	10.1	65.0	17.7	7.9	0.4
Cereal flakes and bran	14	359.9	6.1	1.1	12.9	58.0	1.0	10.5	0.0	60	361.2	6.0	1.1	13.4	57.4	1.4	10.3	0.0
Yoghurt products	217	89.0	3.2	2.1	3.8	10.6	9.6	0.1	0.1	867	82.5	3.1	2.0	3.7	9.7	9.0	0.6	0.1
Flavoured yogurt	135	96.8	3.1	2.0	3.9	12.8	11.8	0.1	0.1	361	101.9	3.5	2.3	4.0	13.2	12.2	0.5	0.1
Flavoured yogurt drinks	14	72.4	1.6	1.0	3.5	11.9	11.2	0.0	0.1	191	73.8	1.7	1.1	3.0	11.3	10.6	0.8	0.1
Plain yogurt	56	71.6	3.6	2.3	4.3	4.4	4.1	0.0	0.1	273	63.7	3.3	2.1	4.1	4.4	4.2	0.4	0.1
Yogurt imitates	12	102.8	3.9	3.0	1.7	12.1	8.6	0.3	0.2	42	77.0	3.7	2.2	2.5	8.0	5.6	1.1	0.1

*Notes: N=Number of items; Units: ENE (kJ) – energy; FAT (g); FASAT (g) – saturated fat; PROT (g) – proteins; CH (g) – carbohydrates; SUG (g) - sugar, FIB (g) – fibre; SALT (g)

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Table 8: Comparison of energy content in the selected food categories
 (in kJ per 100 g or mL per food/drink)

Category	N (VKJ)	ENE Average	SD	ENE Median	N (CLAS)	ENE Average	SD	ENE Median	P -value
Beverages	333	33.3	25.1	33.7	1664	35.8	31.0	37.7	0.111
Fruit and vegetable juices	133	46.0	25.2	46.0	596	47.6	24.8	46.8	0.256
Juices	106	47.8	27	47.8	368	45.6	12.9	46.6	0.686
Nectars	27	38.8	14.2	43.0	228	50.9	36.5	47.8	0.003
Soft drinks	200	24.9	21.3	21.1	1068	29.2	32.2	29.0	0.015
Energy drinks	18	20.8	21.6	10.5	138	33.3	21.5	45.6	0.089
Other soft drinks	182	25.3	21.3	22.2	930	28.6	33.4	27.1	0.122
Breakfast cereals	239	392.6	65.7	387.0	546	396.8	40.2	388.1	0.908
Breakfast cereals	225	394.6	67.2	392.2	486	401.2	39.6	391.7	0.603
Cereal flakes and bran	14	359.9	10.9	358.9	60	361.2	24.2	365.9	0.695
Yoghurt products	217	89.0	39.2	84.6	867	82.5	31.2	77.9	0.017
Flavoured yogurt	135	96.8	39.0	89.1	361	101.9	24.5	94.1	<0.001
Flavoured yogurt drinks	14	72.4	17.7	75.6	191	73.8	13.7	73.8	0.495
Plain yogurt	56	71.6	37.4	59.5	273	63.7	34.4	59.2	0.129
Yogurt imitates	12	102.8	37.3	94.6	42	77.0	24.2	78.7	0.001

*Notes: Data provided on the level of sub-categories for those sub-categories with at least 10 identified unique products per dataset; N=Number of items in dataset; Units: ENE (kJ) – energy *Bold for statistically significant difference (P <0.05)

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Table 9: Comparison of sugar content in the selected food categories
 (in grams per 100 g or mL per food/drink)

	N (VKJ)	SUGAR Average	SD	SUG Median	N (CLAS)	SUGAR Average	SD	SUG Median	P-value
Beverages	333	6.9	6.2	7.4	1664	7.6	6.1	8.4	0.023
Fruit and vegetable juices	133	8.7	3.7	9.8	596	9.5	4.6	9.9	0.218
Juices	106	8.6	3.7	9.6	368	9.2	3.1	9.6	0.651
Nectars	27	9.0	3.5	10.0	228	10.1	6.3	10.2	0.288
Soft drinks	200	5.7	7.2	4.6	1068	6.6	6.6	6.5	0.003
Energy drinks	18	3.3	5.1	0.0	138	7.5	5.3	10.6	0.005
Other soft drinks	182	6.0	7.3	5.0	930	6.5	6.8	6.1	0.093
Breakfast cereals	239	14.0	9.9	15.0	546	15.9	10.2	16.8	0.021
Breakfast cereals	225	14.8	9.7	16.0	486	17.7	9.3	18.0	<0.001
Cereal flakes and bran	14	1.0	0.3	1.1	60	1.4	2.2	1.0	0.873
Yoghurt products	217	9.6	4.2	11.0	867	9.0	4.3	10.7	0.104
Flavoured yogurt	135	11.8	2.8	12.0	361	12.2	2.8	12.1	0.049
Flavoured yogurt drinks	14	11.2	1.6	11.4	191	10.6	2.4	11.3	0.544
Plain yogurt	56	4.1	1.3	4.3	273	4.2	0.9	4.3	0.539
Yogurt imitates	12	8.6	4.7	11.3	42	5.6	4.5	6.1	0.015

*Notes: Data provided on the level of sub-categories for those sub-categories with at least 10 identified unique products per dataset; N=Number of items in dataset; Units: SUG (g) – sugar; *Bold for statistically significant difference (P <0.05)

7. Conclusion

We have successfully compiled a branded food database from datasets using different collection and data management approaches. Previously collected data originated from open access and non-open access sources and was harmonised with consideration of the parameters available in the datasets.

The task focused on beverages, breakfast cereals and yoghurts, food categories which are typically targets in sugar reduction reformulation strategies. The food composition data included in the final dataset included all mandatory nutrition declaration parameters (energy, fats, saturated fat, carbohydrates, sugar, protein and salt) and dietary fibre content, which is part of voluntarily labelling. Data provided in ingredient lists were also included. With considerable variation in the original datasets used, data was missing for some parameters in many cases, but this is not expected to impact on the use of the compiled dataset in WP5.

Along with existing data, new data was collected with the use of a traditional food monitoring study in food stores (CLAS dataset), and through the exploitation of crowd sourcing with the use of a mobile phone application #VešKajJeš (VKJ dataset). The same parameters were collected, as described above. As these two datasets were collected simultaneously, they were compared, to determine if crowd sourcing technique could in future substitute very time demanding data collections in food stores. Comparison of both datasets showed that crowdsourcing is a very useful approach to collect data on new food products on the market. In most cases differences in the median energy and sugar content were minor, however, this was not the case in all the (sub)categories. We could not provide a general pattern, because the direction of the difference was contrary in different food (sub)categories or nutrients. In the food (sub)categories with lower number of products in the dataset (i.e., yoghurt imitates), the differences were typically greater than in the categories with many products. The limitation for comparison of crowdsourcing approach is that this was mostly newly launched products were collected, while the traditional monitoring in food stores collected data systematically on all foods. The other difference is that crowdsourcing probably more commonly provide data for more popular products (with higher market share), while the monitoring in food stores evenly collect data for market-leading and niche products. Further research should be focused into exploitation of differences also with consideration of market-share differences.

The data collected and collated in this task will be further exploited in the WP5 demonstrator (Task 5.1.2 Food labelling data and reformulation tools).

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Supplementary Table S1: Examples of labelling information on prepacked foods in the EU and typical data format

(Sources: [5, 6]).

Information	Mandatory labelling*	Conditionally mandatory	Non-mandatory labelling
The name of the food [text]	Name of the food shall be its legal name. In the absence of such a name, the name of the food shall be its customary name, or, if there is no customary name or the customary name is not used, a descriptive name of the food shall be provided.		
The list of ingredients [text]	It shall include all the ingredients of the food, in descending order of weight, as recorded at the time of their use in the manufacture of the food.	Annex II of Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 includes a list of food substances or products causing allergies or intolerances. Those substances are considered the most common food allergens and shall be indicated in the list of ingredients with a clear reference to the name of the substance or product as listed in Annex II and shall be emphasised through a typeset that clearly distinguishes it from the rest of the list of ingredients.	
The quantity of certain ingredients [text]		The indication of the quantity of an ingredient or category of ingredients (QUID) is required where the ingredient or category of ingredients concerned (a) appears in the name of the food or is usually	

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Information	Mandatory labelling*	Conditionally mandatory	Non-mandatory labelling
		associated with that name by the consumer; (b) is emphasised on the labelling in words, pictures or graphics; or (c) is essential to characterise a food and to distinguish it from products with which it might be confused because of its name or appearance.	
The net quantity [number, unit]	The net quantity of a food shall be expressed using litres, centilitres, millilitres, kilograms or grams, as appropriate: (a) in units of volume in the case of liquid products; (b) in units of mass in the case of other products.		
The nutrition declaration [nutrient, number, unit]	The mandatory nutrition declaration shall include the following: (a) energy value; and (b) the amounts of fat, saturates, carbohydrate, sugars, protein and salt. Typically, these are expressed per 100 g or per 100 ml, with some exceptions.		The content of the mandatory nutrition declaration may be supplemented with an indication of the amounts of one or more of the (a) mono-unsaturates; (b) polyunsaturates; (c) polyols; (d) starch; (e) fibre; (f) vitamins or minerals
Content of specific ingredients, i.e., caffeine, sweeteners, ... [text / number, unit]		Beverages with high caffeine content or foods with added caffeine: Caffeine content statements	

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Information	Mandatory labelling*	Conditionally mandatory	Non-mandatory labelling
		<p>Foods containing a sweetener or sweeteners: Official (labelled) name of the food need to include wording 'with sweetener(s)'.</p> <p>Foods containing aspartame/ aspartame-acesulfame salt: Statements on foods containing aspartame</p> <p>Foods containing more than 10% added polyols: The statement 'excessive consumption may produce laxative effects'</p>	
Nutrition and/or health claims [text]		Content of ingredient mentioned in the claim is conditionally mandatory (only when claims are used).	Foods can be labelled with nutrition and/or health claims.